

**A STUDY ON LIBRARY USE BY CHENNAI MEDICAL
COLLEGE HOSPITAL AND RESEARCH CENTRE
STUDENTS AND FACULTIES AT TRICHY**

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Introduction:

Information is all around us and is the staple diet of human beings. Information is variously perceived as facts, intelligence, data, news and knowledge. Information has been a common ingredient to all areas of human endeavour, be it the day to day affairs of business, matters of life and death or the most trivial pursuits. In a modern industrial society there are negligibly few individuals, who do not, from time to time, occasionally/frequently have any requirement of information. It is an essential accompaniment of almost every social activity. Information is considered as important that contributes towards the development of a nation. It provides the core for the development of knowledge, the basis for innovations, the resources for informed citizenry and as a result become a key commodity for the progress of a society. Members of a society acquire the needed information from a variety of sources. However several of these sources are expensive, complex or difficult for individuals to acquire and use. Therefore, the role of libraries becomes vital in meeting the information needs of individuals in the society. Libraries develop their collections, facilities and services to meet the information needs of their patrons. A health or medical library is designed to assist physicians, health professionals, students, patients, consumers and medical researchers to improve, update, access or evaluate health care. The library is the most preferred source of information for gathering information for the medical students and the teaching faculties. Teachers, laboratories, and libraries are important components in providing effective medical education. The main purpose of medical library is to support medical education, including teaching, research and patient – care. Just as a healthy brain is essential for a healthy human being, a healthy library is an asset for promotion and advancement of health science in health education. In medical libraries, the latest technologies are increasingly used to collect, store, retrieve and disseminate a great amount of information to help medical professionals in their day-to-day education, research and clinical practices. The medical websites and database developed by medical institutions, associations, agencies, and publishers provide the latest information. In a developing country like India, medical professionals are quite aware of the new technologies used by their counterparts in the developed nations. Despite of enormous money spent for library and information sciences, the utilization of library and information sciences by medical students and faculties were not studied much.

Review of Literature:

Library use survey of University of Texas Health Science Center at San Antonio Faculty in the year 2000 revealed that majority of the users considered library resources and services as essential to their professional productivity. A change was also observed between the usage patterns of library as 56% users were connecting to library by computers against the 32% users in 1996, and about 40% users favoured the need to increase fee/ additional fee to get more revenue for library (Rathnakara *et al.*, 2011). A study titled "The Utilization of Archival Information by Researchers in Kenya: A case study of the University of Nairobi" revealed that researchers were using variety of information resources to meet their information, and relied more on archival personnel to access information. A study on "Use of College Libraries by Faculty Members of University of Delhi" has brought out that textbooks were most frequently used resources, followed by, reference books and general books. Main purpose of visiting library was to prepare notes to students. Faculty also highlighted the inadequacy of Journals and textbooks. Almost all the faculty members favoured need for computerization of their libraries (Lal *et al.*, 1999). A study from Malaysian University revealed that teachers played an important role in promoting the use of libraries by students. Authors were not satisfied with students' library use skills, and hence students expected from librarians to provide a comfortable academic environment in library (Adikata *et al.*, 2006). Goel *et al.* (2012) conducted a study on Library Usage by Undergraduate

Medical students in a Medical college in North India. The study revealed that maximum students were in the age group of 18-25 years. 64.5% students visited library for updating their knowledge, 31.7% for retrieving literature, 18.7% for information on a specific disease, 12.6% for research purposes, 6.7% for diagnosis, 2.6% for publications, 2.2% for patient care. Among the IT services available 57% used computer, 54.1% utilised internet, 47.01% used E-mail, 32.5% used E-books, 31.3% used CD ROM and 28.3% used telephone. Out of benefits available of using IT services 75.7% said it lead to better access of information, 51.8% said it provided quick information, 42.9% said it lead to contact with distant personnel, 44.75% believed it lead to improvement of quality of work, 22.7% said it lead to decrease in use of postal mail, 10.8% said it lead to decrease in use of telephone, 10.1% said it lead to decrease in use of printed version. 34.3% (91 students) opined that there was need for an orientation programme regarding the use of IT services in the library.

Aim and Objectives:

The main aim is to find out the use of library and information sciences by medical students and faculty members.

- ✓ To find out the frequency of visit to the library.
- ✓ To know the purpose of visit to the library.
- ✓ To elicit the preferred mode of information resources.
- ✓ To determine the level of satisfaction among the various user groups.

Data Collection Procedure:

A survey method was adopted for this study. The data was collected through the structural questionnaire. A total of 1000 participants, there were 470 males and 530 females. They were undergraduate students (874), faculty (72), doctors (38), postgraduate students (10) and research scholars (6). Which includes (UG Students, PG students, Faculty, Doctors, Research scholars from various departments like Medical, Dental, Nursing, Pharmacy and Physiotherapy). A questionnaire was given to each person and they were explained about the purpose of filling each questionnaire. The questionnaire consisted of basic data, frequency, purpose and preferred mode of resource; and consultation with library staff, physical facilities, training aspects and others. 1000 out of 1000 questionnaire were collected. Good responses for this questionnaire. Questionnaire was used in order to get accurate information.

Observations and Results:

The study was conducted among 1000 people. It includes Doctors, Faculties, Research Scholars, Undergraduate and postgraduate students of Medical and Dental fraternity, and Faculties and Undergraduate students of nursing, pharmacy and physiotherapy. Out of them 53% were females and 47% were males. The distribution of gender is depicted in

Figure 1.

Among the people participated, 87.4% were undergraduate students, 7.2% were faculty members, 3.8% were Doctors, 1% were postgraduate students, 0.6% were Research scholars

Figure 2

Out of 1000 participants, 79.8% belonged to Medical fraternity, 9.6% to dental field, 5% to nursing, 4.9% to pharmacy and 0.7% to physiotherapy and the details are given in

Figure 3

During analysis, it was found out that, among 1000 participants, 7.1% visited library daily, 19.4% weekly, 31.2% monthly, 19.8% visited several times a year and 22.4% visited occasionally (Figure 4).

Purpose of Visiting Library:

On analysing the purpose of visiting the library, 68.5% of participants visited library always to study, 19.5% of them visited sometimes to study, 8.1% participants visited only rarely and 3.8% visited library for other purposes (Figure 5)

From the above figure (Figure 6), it is clear that, 16.8% of 1000 participants visited library to meet friends always, 57.1% visited sometimes to meet friends, 15.5% visited rarely to Meet friends and 10.5% never used library as a meeting place of their friends.

Among 1000 participants, 19.7% always came to the library to gather some information, 50.7% visited sometimes to get information, 24.2% visited rarely for the same and 5.3% never used library to get information (Figure 7).

With regard to borrowing/ returning/ renewal of books, 15.3% always availed the opportunity, whereas the rest availed it either sometimes or rarely or never. Details are provided in Figure 8.

With reference to use of library for reading journals and magazines, 15.7% participants always availed the opportunity, 36.8% sometimes and 32% rarely and details are furnished in Figure 9.

Newspaper reading was one another reason for visiting library among 89.8% only. The details regarding regularity or otherwise is given in Figure 10.

Use of CD ROMs as a source of learning was utilised by 59.9% among the study group, 11.1% availed this opportunity regularly. The details are shown in Figure 11.

It is not uncommon for a reader to relax in the library. However, 14% availed this always and details in relation to other participants are given in Figure 12.

Though library is a common place for drinking water, it is surprising to note that 233 (23.3%) participants never utilised this facility as given in Figure13.

Preferred Mode of Information Resources:

The preferred mode of information resources was books, reference sources, journals, CD ROMs, online information, and E journals among the participants. However, usage was variable and details with regard to the resource are furnished in Figures 14, 15, 16, 17, 18 and 19 respectively.

Consulting Library Staff:

Library staff being qualified and experienced with their library, many a times students and faculty consult them for their requirements if they had difficulty. Among the participants of the study, it was variable with regard to books, journals, periodicals, information resources, references and CD ROMs and the details are provided in Figures 20, 21, 22, 23, 24 and 25 respectively.

Need for Information:

The need for information was analysed with regard to research project and they were preparation for teaching/ seminar/ symposium, updating knowledge, and entrance examination. Majority use the library for doing research project and it was followed by other purposes. The details are depicted in figures 26, 27, 28 and 29 respectively

Use of Computer Based Services:

Computer has become an integrated part of learning among students and faculty of different branch of health sciences. The analysis revealed that the usage was not uniform among the students and faculty. They used it either to check E-mail or chatting or internet or online data collection or E-journals for which the details are furnished in figures 30, 31, 32, 33 and 34 respectively.

Preference of Mode of Information:

Library though provides different forms of information, 10.5% people preferred manual access of information as given in Figure 35.

Physical Facilities:

Physical facilities are an integral part of any library as the end users spend quite a lot of time and hence their expectations vary from each other. The physical facilities opined in relation to furniture/ seating arrangement, reading area, air conditioning, library environment, printing, photocopy, scanning and toilet by the end users are provided in figures 36, 37, 38, 39, 40, 41, 42, 43 and 44 respectively.

Training on Library Usage:

In general, training on library usage is rarely and hence only 5.2% answered yes for this questionnaire (Figure 45). Though modern students and faculty are familiar with technology, 5.1% of the end users wanted to have training on usage of library science in the form of lecture/ other means (Figure 46).

Conclusion:

In the present study, it was found out that, all the participants used the library to the maximum extent to collect information for teaching, training and research and they have informed that different sources are available for collecting information. Viz., printed materials like books, journals, periodicals, CD ROMs and

internet facilities to collect information. The participants were of view that the ambience and amenities provided in the library were likely to enhance their use of library.

Summary:

A total of 1000 participants, there were 470 males and 530 females. They were undergraduate students (874), faculty (72), doctors (38), postgraduate students (10) and research scholars (6). Among the 1000, 685 (68.5%) visited library regularly for studying. Library is also a place to meet friends (57.1%), get information (50.7%), borrow/ return/ renew books (15.3%), read journals/ magazines (36.8%), and newspapers (50.4%); watch CD ROMs (11.1%), drink water (42%), and relax (46.6%). By and large, participants prefer books for information (45.5%), reference source (53.2%) and journals (33.1%), and less from CD - ROM. Only 29.3% Consulted librarian for information. Participants used library for getting information for their teaching purpose (50.5%), writing research reports (37.4%), updating (35.1%) and preparing for entrance examination (38.1%). Electronic technologies available at library used by participants were E-mail (39.6%), internet (36.4%) and E-journals (31.8%). However, 77.7% of the participants used electronic and manual methods available at library. Ambience of library such as lighting/ ventilation and furniture were good as per 67.7% and 51.7% respectively. Though advances have developed in library sciences, only 5.2% wanted training on library sciences.

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